

Designing Experiments for Controller Perturbation Theories — an Example

Allan L. White and Hagbae Kim
NASA Langley Research Center
Hampton, VA 23681-0001
Tel: 1-804-864-6199 or 864-6264
Email: Allan.White@qmgate.larc.nasa.gov
hbkim@larc.nasa.gov

Abstract—Recent theoretical results have extended the reliability analysis for real-time digital control systems to cover temporary periods of controller misbehavior. Previously, reliability analyses assumed the controller always had to be in control, and periods of controller misbehavior were either ignored or declared to be system failure. It is possible, however, for a system to survive repeated controller perturbations because of plant dynamics. System inertia can prevent an incorrect command from leading to immediate catastrophe, and this time lag gives the controller an opportunity to recover. Recent advances place this idea on a quantitative basis by deriving results for the basic control criterion of asymptotic stability in terms of matrix norms.

Translating a theoretical result into a laboratory experiment poses numerous problems and possibilities. We present the results of the experiment inducing some transmission perturbations on communication cable due to radiating EMI in the reverberation chamber. We consider four topics such as (i) parameter observation, (ii) predictive ability, (iii) asymptotic stability, and (iv) field data.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Most electronic and electrical equipments are not only potential sources of ElectroMagnetic Interference (EMI) but also victims not functioning as designed at certain levels of ambient EM. This phenomena becomes more significant for digital machines like digital control-computers automating the command and control performances in modern control plants. The effects of EMI on those controllers range from simple annoyance to catastrophe.

In such a harsh environment as EMI, a control computer is likely to be subject to massive transient faults, which induces upsets in the controller even if the computer uses redundant elements. During the upset caused

by EMI, the computer itself can send arbitrary (mostly incorrect) commands to the actuators. In this paper, we assume the effects of EMI are transient. In most previous reliability and performance analyses for digital control systems, those temporal periods of controller misbehavior (or upset) are either ignored by the assumption that the controller should always be in control or declared to be system failure. However, it is possible for a system to survive repeated controller perturbation temporarily because of plant dynamics. System inertia can prevent a wrong command from leading to immediate catastrophe, and this time lag gives the controller an opportunity to recover. Recent advances place this idea on a quantitative basis by deriving results for the basic control criterion of asymptotic stability in terms of matrix norms.

In [2], the authors proposed an analytic method to derive the maximum upset time for a class of control system disturbances by examining system stability or state residence in the allowed state space, where the idea of stability-in-the-mean was introduced. In [1], random interval matrices accounting for those malfunctions were considered and a Kronecker product formulation was used to conclude asymptotic convergence. In [3], a theorem about stability using matrix actions on the system was developed, which gives a more reasonable approach to test system stability rather than using eigenvalues under time-varying system matrices.

In this paper, we describe an initial effort to translate theoretical results into laboratory experiments.¹ Specifically, we consider five topics such as (i) parameter observation, (ii) predictive ability, (iii) asymptotic stability, and (iv) field data.

¹There are some partial successes and some remaining open problems, which will be mentioned later.

First, and most important, is whether or not the parameters required by the theory can be observed. The current theories require a description of the disturbance in terms of a matrix action on the system, and a problem is collecting enough data during a disturbance to (uniquely) determine this matrix. A partial solution was obtained for this problem which includes the engineering case of common noise on the communication network. This observation problem inspired some additional efforts in theoretical development. Unfortunately, all attempts (to date) to construct a theory based on just input/output ratios (instead of the entire matrix action) have ended in counterexamples. One such counterexample is given in Section 3.

Second, a good theoretical framework should permit extensive conclusions from modest experiments (predictive ability). It was decided to study the effects of network disturbances on asymptotic stability by the simple experiment of adding electromagnetic noise to a byte stream. There was no plant or control law present at the time of the experiment. Under the assumption that disturbances last only one control cycle and are geometrically distributed, the current theories were able to successfully interpret the data and make assertions about asymptotic stability for an arbitrarily chosen plant and control law.

The third and fourth topics— asymptotic stability and field data—are closely related for this experiment. The third is how to make conclusions about asymptotic stability in a finite experiment. The solution involves the fourth topic – what information is required from field data. This paper uses the likelihood of a disturbance to determine asymptotic stability.

In Section 2, the characteristics of EMI are described focusing on its effects on digi-

tal machines. Our approach studying only the effects of transmission disturbances on system stability for features of EMI upsets is also mentioned, and a certain terminology and the definition of system stability are presented there. Section 3 considers the procedure needed for the experiments dealing with network disturbances, where the first and second topics are investigated with a reasonable conjecture and its counterexample in treating input/output ratios of a system. In Section 4, we illustrate pre-experiment tests investigating the effects of EMI on the equipments, especially the electro-optical converter. Section 5 describes the experiment. Section 6 interprets the data obtained through experiments inducing some upsets on transmission lines due to some resonant frequencies. The third and fourth topics are discussed by using the results of the experiments. This paper concludes with Section 7, which contains the summary and plans for future work.

2. BACKGROUND AND PROBLEMS

The effects of EMI are extremely variable in character and magnitude ranging from trivial annoyance to catastrophe. Since modern digital systems are likely to be more sensitive to this EMI than their analog predecessors, the investigation and analysis for the EMI effects on both digital control-computers and plants are key to the verification of the system's integrity (e.g., to the reliability model). The sources of EMI are classified into *man-made* and *natural*. In most cases, the natural sources of radiation such as atmospheric noise during lightening and cosmic noise are likely to have a broad-band of frequency. However, the man-made emissions like radio and television broadcasting can be concentrated in certain narrow-bands of frequencies.

In this paper, we consider a simple system represented by:

$$x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k), \quad (2.1)$$

where x and u are the system state and input vectors. We also suppose that the only input is the feedback from the state vector and its unperturbed form is:

$$u(k) = Fx(k), \quad (2.2)$$

which gives the equation:

$$x(k+1) = Ax(k) + BFx(k) = (A + BF)x(k). \quad (2.3)$$

Although there are various aspects of those potential malfunctions, we primarily consider loss or corruption of transmission of data in digital systems. Specifically, we deal with transmission perturbations between sensors/actuators and the computing processors (i.e., on the actuators/sensors lines). The experiments also simulate corrupting the sensor (or actuator) signals. This disturbances is represented by a sensor garble matrix G_s , which is equal to an identity matrix in case of no upset. Eq. 2.3 becomes:

$$x(k+1) = (A + BFG_s)x(k). \quad (2.4)$$

By combining an actuator garble matrix G_a obtained similarly, we can write the disturbed system-equation as:

$$x(k+1) = (A + BG_aFG_s)x(k). \quad (2.5)$$

Since these garble matrices may be different at each time frame according to the behaviors of upsets, they can be modeled by either functions of time index k or certain random sequences. By including the effects of these garble matrices (which should be modeled or estimated via experiments), we can examine system stability.

Figure. 1 (a) Ordinary Asymptotic Stability and (b) Strong Asymptotic Stability, in the Presence of Repeated Disturbances

3. THEORETIC WORK

In this section, we present the theory supporting the experiments, and consider the procedure needed for the experiments dealing with network disturbances, where the first and second topics mentioned in Section 1 are investigated with a reasonable conjecture and its counterexample in treating input/output ratios of a system.

Theory about Matrix Norms

We now review the basic theory for the experiment and consider the procedure needed for an trial in an experiment of perturbing the sensor (or actuator) lines. We assume that the controlled plant is subjected to a sequence of matrix actions which are independent and identically distributed.²

Ordinary asymptotic stability considers system behavior with respect to a single perturbation — the effect of a disturbances vanishes as time goes to infinity. Strong asymptotic stability considers system behavior with respect to multiple perturbations — the effect also vanishes as time

²The validity of this assumption requires more study, however it seems reasonable if we combine a number of correlated actions resulting from a single failure and consider as a single action.

goes to infinity in the presence of additional (stationarily-occurring) disturbances. The difference is illustrated in Fig. 1. Throughout this paper, we concern strong asymptotic stability for all the results. Then, we can use the following theorem which is proved in [3]:

Theorem *Consider a system is subjected to a countably infinite number of matrix operation, and the norm of these matrix operations are independent and identically distributed random variables. If the expected value of the norm is less than one, then the system is strongly-asymptotically stable with probability one.*

This theorem is invaluable due to the following sub-multiplicative property:

$$|W_1 W_2 \cdots W_n v| \leq \|W_1\| \|W_2\| \cdots \|W_n\| |v|, \quad \forall n \text{ and } \forall v, \quad (3.6)$$

where W_k is a system matrix at time index i (i.e., $x(k+1) = W(k)x(k)$).

A Reasonable Conjecture and Its Counterexample

There are various norms for system matrices. In order to have the sub-multiplicative property, a norm should indicate the maximal action of the matrix over the entire vector space. Thus, we need sufficient infor-

mation about any perturbation to determine the global properties of the perturbation. Note that if we obtain the average input-output relationship of the matrix actions in the presence of a perturbation, it would be a more convenient criteria for asymptotic stability. In other words, we need any input v selected according to a certain distribution and the corresponding output Wv in this case, and we just examine whether or not the average value of the ratio $|Wv|/|v|$ is larger than one. A result of this type depends on the joint distribution of the matrices and vectors.

Now we present a counterexample in the space \mathcal{R}^3 . Consider the system represented by:

$$x(k+1) = W(k)x(k),$$

where the matrix $W(k)$ is equal to W_1 with probability 1/2 or W_2 with probability 1/2:

$$W_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{10} & \frac{1}{10} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix}; \quad W_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{10} & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Suppose the initial vector is $v_0 = [1 \ 0 \ 0]^T$. The system is stable if W_1 occurs first. It is unstable if W_2 occurs first. Hence, it is said to be unstable with probability one-half. But the expected output/input ratio is $\frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{15}{12} = \frac{27}{40} < 1$.

We again consider the system in more detail as $x(k_1) = (A + BF_i)x(n)$, where A and B are constant matrices and F are varying (perturbed). Suppose the system is controllable and the unperturbed system is stable by having a norm less than one:

$$\|A + BF_1\| < 1.$$

For an example under these conditions, let:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix}; \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix},$$

then:

$$F_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{10} & \frac{4}{10} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \quad F_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{4}{10} & 0 \\ -2 & 0 & -\frac{3}{2} \end{bmatrix},$$

where each with probability $\frac{1}{2}$ satisfies the detailed system requirements and yields the original counterexample matrices of W_1 and W_2 . This example suggests considering the controller in more detail from the point of view of control theory. There is a lack of reachability and self-stabilization in the feedback system above. If it gets on the wrong track, it stays there.

Procedure needed for the experiment

In fact, $W(k)$ of each time index can be obtained from the value of G_s and G_a at that time by using Eq. (2.5). Samples of signal perturbations are used to determine the garble matrices, and hence to estimate the mean of $\|W(k)\|$.

- The sensor reads the state of the system, and the signal from the sensor is both stored and sent out on the sensor line.
- The disturbance is applied to the sensor line.
- The signal through transmission lines in the presence of radiated interference is received and stored.
- The feedback computer and the actuator perform on the received signal to evolve the system state.

The cycle above may continued for a period after the disturbance has disappeared so as to confirm that there is no lingering effect from the disturbance — we already assumed that the effects of EMI are temporal. All these cycles compose one trial.

For each cycle, suppose $x(k)$ is the state of the system in the first step and $z(k)$ is the signal received and stored in the third step. Then, we can obtain one sample of garble matrix G_s from $z(k) = G_s x(k)$. The theory requires that the matrices be independent random sequences, which is already shown as a reasonable assumption by grouping actions of correlated cycles. In other words, if the trial consists of cycles k_1, \dots, k_m , then the matrix of a single action, M , can be obtained by their product, i.e.,:

$$M = \prod_{i=1}^m [A + BFG_s(k)],$$

where $G_s(k)$ denotes the k -th sample of G_s . It is true that a single input-output relation does not uniquely determine a garble matrix (or its norm). However, if we assume that the corrupted version of a signal depends only on the signal and noise (i.e. independent of other signals), we can obtain uniquely a garble matrix as a diagonal matrix $G_s(k) = \text{Diag}[g_s^i(k)]$, where $g_s^i(k) = z_i(k)/x_i(k)$. This assumption makes sense considering that the signals are sent either serially or through different lines. Some statistical tests are performed to examine the property of independence among those signals using experiment data in Section 4, which verifies the quality of data.³

4. PRE-EXPERIMENT TESTS

This section describes the electrical engineering procedure of determining how the EMI corrupted the signal. This issue is separate from the control theory work, but it

³For some systems it may not possible to arrange the experiment and observations in a manner that permits estimating the garble matrices. For these situations an extension of theory is required, which is underway.

is of interest to system designers and experimenters. We offer it as material with its own intrinsic value.

EMI experiments to access its effects on the digital systems should be planned like Fig. 2-(b), where EMI affects only transmission lines and (avionics) interfaces. The experiment facilities like a Electric/Optic (E/O) converter should be completely shielded against EMI, because this kind of equipment is needed for the sake of conducting the experiment. However, our experiment is performed like Fig. 2-(a) for the problem of feasibility, where the level of shielding E/O converters will be examined via pre-experiments.

This experiment is to cause upsets on the communication loop due to noise induced by the radiating Radio Frequency (RF) field in the reverberation chamber, as depicted in Fig. 3. Although there are two modes of EMI coupling, radiated and conducted, E/O converters can avoid propagating EMI effects outside the chamber through the conducted mode of coupling. (Note that the conducted path may be resistive, or some inductance and capacitance, or combination of these.) The Multi-Link Transceiver (MLT) is placed within the isolated cable tray located under the floor of chamber. An about 18 feet of twisted pair shielded cable is connected to the MLT transmit, out into the chamber, draped around in free-space within the HIRF chamber, and returning back to the receive terminal connection. The cable shields are connected to an earth ground, as shown in Fig. 3, inside of the tray. In addition to the MLT, an EM-field sensor system is used to measure an the electric field intensity within isolated cable tray. Once these devices are secure, the chamber is closed and the stirrer rotates with a certain speed (e.g., 5 revolutions per minute) and the signal having a certain frequency and power level is radiated

Figure 2. (a) Actual Experiment and (b) Ideal (Future) Experiment

Figure 3. False Signal Transmission Test Set-up

Table 1. Entire-Ensemble Test

[MHz]\[W]	55	100	150
275.9	no	no	no
285.2	no	yes	yes
290.1	no	yes	yes
414.2	no	yes	yes
435.3	no	yes	yes
496.2	no	yes	yes
524.0	yes	yes	yes
537.6	yes	yes	yes
639.5	no	no	yes
724.5	no	no	no
738.6	no	no	no
759.1	no	no	no
759.5	no	no	no
792.0	no	no	no
815.0	no	no	no
817.3	no	no	no
837.2	no	no	no
951.0	no	no	no
986.9	no	no	no
993.0	no	no	no

from the antenna into the chamber. An oscilloscope is also connected to the transmit and receive terminal strip, of the up-stream MLT to observe any false signal transmission in the communication loop.

Priorly to the experiment for obtaining sample data of upsets, we conducted four pre-experiment tests: (i) the entire-ensemble test, (ii) the radiating-wave test, (iii) the low-powered-resonance test, and (iv) the noise-on-the-line test.

The Entire-Ensemble Test

The entire-ensemble test was a HIRF chamber test that subjected the system to various frequency and power levels. Because of the chamber size and available equipment, the

frequency range was from 250Mh to 1000Mh. The power sent into the chamber ranged up to 200 watts sustained or 500 watts for short periods. Because of a lack of equipment, the actual power received by the antenna is not known (impedance mismatch). In addition, there were no probes available to measure the volts/meter in the chamber.

Initially, twenty test frequencies were used. They were chosen at random to avoid repetition and patterns. Table 1 shows the results of an entire ensemble test, where *no* indicates no upset detected and *yes* for some upsets. The stirrer speed was 5 *rev/min*. A thirteen second byte stream was sent, which consisted of ramps using values from 0 to 255.

The Radiating-Wire Test

This test checked if the E/O converter was being upset by an RF field radiating into the protective tray by the leads or shielding of the shielded twisted pair. The first E/O converter was left connected to the twisted pair and powered up, but the optical cables were connected to a second E/O converter placed adjacent to the first in the tray. Short wires, kept entirely in the tray, were used for the electrical connection for the second E/O converter. This is clarified in Fig. 4.

This test used a stirrer speed of 1 *rev/min*, and the byte *b3* (hex) was sent continuously for one minute. The initial power levels were 100 *watts* and 200 *watts*. Additional tests, at different power levels, were conducted at 414.2 [MHz] when a disturbance was noted at 200 *watts*. Table 2 presents the results of this test.

The Low-Power-Resonance Test

There were two parts to the low-power-resonance test. For the first part, an oscil-

Figure 4. Inside the Cable Tray for (a) the Entire-Ensemble Test and (b) the Radiating-Wire.

Table 2. Radiating-Wire test

[MHz]\[W]	100	125	150	200
275.9	no	—	—	no
285.2	no	—	—	no
290.1	no	—	—	no
414.2	no	yes	yes	yes
435.3	no	—	—	no
496.2	no	—	—	no
524.0	no	—	—	no
537.6	no	—	—	no
639.5	no	—	—	no
724.5	no	—	—	no
738.6	no	—	—	no
759.1	no	—	—	no
759.5	no	—	—	no
792.0	no	—	—	no
815.0	no	—	—	no
817.3	no	—	—	no
837.2	no	—	—	no
951.0	no	—	—	no
986.9	no	—	—	no
993.0	no	—	—	no

loscope was attached to the E/O converter outside the chamber that electrically connected to the Heurikon (which normally sent the byte stream). No bytes were sent. The test checked if the RF field in the chamber would cause the ensemble (wire in the chamber and converter in the tray) to send a noise induced signal that would trigger the oscilloscope. The stirrer speed was 1 rev/min, and the test lasted one minute. The results are listed in Table 3.

The second part checked the corruption of a byte stream at low power, yielding Table 4. The computer sent b3 (hex) for one minute. The stirrer speed was 1 rev/min.

The Noise-on-the-Wire Test

This test checked (and established) that at low power the ensemble was being disturbed by noise on the line either conducting or radiating within the E/O converter. Noise was induced by a high frequency coil that enclosed both (short) wires on the E/O converter. An oscilloscope measured the peak-to-peak voltage level of the induced noise. This configuration is sketched in Fig. 5. A byte stream b3 (hex) was sent continuously. The power was slowly increased until the byte stream was disturbed. The results ap-

Table 3. 1st Low-Power-Resonance Test

[MHz]\[W]	2	5	10	25
500	—	—	—	no
510	no	—	—	—
520	no	—	—	—
525	yes	—	—	—
530	yes	—	—	—
535	yes	yes	yes	yes
540	yes	—	—	—
545	yes	—	—	—
550	—	yes	—	yes
555	yes	—	—	—
560	yes	—	—	—
565	yes	—	—	—
570	no	—	—	—
575	no	—	—	no
600	—	—	—	no

Table 4. 2nd Low-Power-Resonance Test

[MHz]\[W]	2	10	200
350	no	—	—
400	no	—	—
450	no	—	—
500	no	—	—
510	no	—	—
520	no	no	no
530	yes	no	yes
540	yes	yes	yes
550	no	yes	yes
560	no	no	yes
570	no	no	no
580	no	—	—
590	no	—	—
600	no	—	—

pear in Table 5.

5. EXPERIMENTS

Because of the results of the electrical engineering tests, it was decided to perform a low power experiment where the disturbance was due to line noise entering the E/O converter. The experiment used continuous-wave power and a stirrer speed of 5 rev/min. Four byte streams were used.

- stream # 1: 2K each of a *uniform* distribution, *normal* distribution, a *sawtooth*, and a *ramp*.
- stream # 2: 8K of *ramp* from 0 to 255
- stream # 3: 2K each of *ramp*, *sawtooth*, *normal* distribution, and *uniform* distribution.
- stream # 4: 8K of *ramp* from 255 to 0.

Table 5. Noise-on-the-Wire Test

[MHz]	[V]	[W]
500	0.605	5.2
510	0.790	5.0
520	0.815	4.9
525	0.855	6.6
530	0.810	6.9
535	0.895	10.0
540	0.735	9.2
550	0.805	9.3
555	0.718	5.5
560	0.720	7.1
565	0.650	3.0
570	0.560	3.1
575	.495	1.3

Figure 5. Noise-on-the-Wire Test

Table 6. Collected Sample Data

[MHz]\[W]	2	5	10	50
475	no	no	no	no
500	no	no	no	no
525	yes	yes	yes	yes
550	yes	yes	yes	yes
575	no	no	no	no

At each frequency and power, stream # 1 and # 2 were each sent five times. If there was no disturbance, the next frequency or power level was selected. If there was a disturbance, stream # 3 and # 4 were each sent five times. The results whether some upsets were observed or not are given in Table 6.

Suppose this transmission lines used in these experiments are the sensor lines. Then, the garble matrix G_s becomes an identity matrix I under the frequencies 475, 500, and 575 [MHz], however it is no longer an identity under 525 and 550 [MHz] due to some upsets. By using all the samples of sent and received signals from the Heurikon (the total number of bytes for the samples is 160K), we

can estimate both the garble matrix G_s and the mean of the system matrix (and thus the mean of its norm).

6. INTERPRETATION

This section returns to the control theory and uses the result in Section 3 to interpret the experimental data.

We deal with a simple system to demonstrate how to use the sample data to examine asymptotic system stability. Suppose system dynamics are governed by the following linear time-invariant equation:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1(k+1) &= 11.02x_1(k) + 1.08x_2(k) + 3.5u_1(k) \\ x_2(k+1) &= 0.95x_2(k) + 0.5u_1(k) + 1.07u_2(k). \end{aligned}$$

When the coefficient matrices of a quadratic performance index are given as $R_{xx} = 10I$ and $R_{uu} = 5I$, we obtain the optimal feedback control gain matrix F that stabilizes the controlled process by solving a discrete

Riccati equation as:

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} -3.1251 & -0.3090 \\ 1.0791 & -0.5512 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then, let W_n be the system matrix in the absence of any disturbance becomes:

$$A + BF = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0822 & -0.0015 \\ -0.4079 & 0.2057 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The original system matrix that has a norm larger than one ($\|A\| = 11.02$) is stabilized by using the optimal control input F , which changes the norm of the system matrix into $\|A + BF\| = 0.4901$. In the presence of some EMI, the norm of the system matrix, becomes random due to the randomness of the garble matrix. We define the system matrix under EMI by W_e , which is represented by $A + BFG_s$, using a random sequence of garble matrix G_s .

For the garble matrix, we also consider the simplest case, where the garble matrix can be obtained as a unique solution from one pair of sent and received signals. This is based on the assumption of isolation among signals. That is, the corrupted version of a signal depends only on that signal and noise (and on no other signals). Practically, this assumption makes sense when one sends the signal serially, or sends the original signals through separate lines and observe the (possibly corrupted) received signals separately before any processing or mixing of signals has initiated. For a more simplicity, we consider 2×2 case, where the sent and received signals are represented by y and z , respectively (i.e., two states of signals are sent serially), then:

$$\begin{bmatrix} z_1 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{11} & g_{12} \\ g_{21} & g_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6.7)$$

Since z_1 depends only on y_1 and noise (i.e., $g_{ij} = 0$ if $i \neq j$) due to the assumption of

independence, Eq. (6.7) becomes:

$$\begin{bmatrix} z_1 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & g_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6.8)$$

Using Eq. (6.8), we consequently obtain the sample of the system matrix by:

$$A + BFG_s = \begin{bmatrix} 11.02 & 1.08 \\ 0 & 0.95 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 3.5 & 0 \\ 0.5 & 1.07 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} g_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & g_{22} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6.9)$$

Table 7 contains both the expected norm of the system matrix computed by those samples and the probability of upset occurrence, for each condition of EMI having the frequency (525 or 550 MHz) and the power level (2, 5, 10, or 50 watts). In every case in the presence of EMI, the system loses its stability because the expected norm of the system matrix becomes larger than one. While the occurrence of upset(s) and its effect (large garble matrix) increase as the power increases at the frequency 525 MHz (which can be shown by the relative magnitude of the mean norm or the probability of upsets), the relation between the power levels and the behaviors of upsets has no clearly-explicit form at 550 MHz. Let P be the probability of EMI presence, then the expected norm of the system matrix over the entire control-mission is equal to:

$$(1 - P)\|W_n\| + PE(\|W_e\|) = (1 - P)\|A + BF\| + PE(\|A + BFG_s\|).$$

This should be smaller than one to maintain asymptotic stability according to *Theorem 1*, that is:

$$(1 - P)\|W_n\| + PE(\|W_e\|) < 1 \implies P < \frac{1 - \|W_n\|}{E(\|W_e\|) - \|W_n\|}.$$

From the above inequality, the maximum value of P maintaining asymptotic stability

Table 7. $E(\|W_e\|)$, P_{max} , and P_f

[MHz]	[W]	$E(\ W_e\)$	P_{max}	P_f
525	2	1.298	0.631	0.040
	5	2.216	0.295	0.087
	10	3.873	0.151	0.183
	50	9.959	0.054	0.474
550	2	2.385	0.269	0.108
	5	1.617	0.452	0.065
	10	1.623	0.450	0.065
	50	1.632	0.447	0.067

is computed for each condition of EMI, as given in Table 7, where the mean norm of the system matrix $E(\|W_e\|)$ and the probability of upsets P_f are also presented.

Consequently, we see that the isolated tray seems to protect the MLT from all frequencies and power levels with some exceptions. The results of these experiments suggest that upsets due to radiating EMI are more sensitive to the frequencies rather than the power levels. We consider certain frequencies are more dominating to induce upsets because of the physical relations between wire lead lengths and the applied frequencies.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper discusses designing and conducting an experiment to support recent theoretical advances in robust control. These advances in control theory derived conditions for maintaining asymptotic stability in the presence of controller disturbances.

Section 2 defines strong asymptotic stability where the error vector converges to zero in the presence of repeated disturbances. In

ordinary asymptotic stability the error vector converges to zero after one disturbance. Section three presents a theorem that gives sufficient conditions for strong asymptotic stability terms of the first moment of the norm. Computing the norm requires that enough observations be made (during an experiment) to determine the global action of a matrix operation. It would be more convenient to have a condition for stability in terms of the average output/input ratio. Section 3 also presents a counterexample to an "average output/input" conjecture.

The original abstract for this paper was submitted on the basis of an experiment that used a coil to disturb signals on a line. After the abstract was submitted, it became possible to perform an experiment in an electromagnetic reverberation chamber. It was decided to perform and report on this experiment because of its greater engineering realism, even though this left less time for data analysis. An obvious example of unexamined data is that the byte strings contain substrings with different distributions (uniform, normal, and ramp). The experiment with the coil on the line gave different results for asymptotic stability for different distributions. The results from the reverberation chamber remain to be analyzed.

Section 4 describes the pre-experiment tests — first to determine if the equipment could be perturbed and second to determine the nature of the perturbation. It was determined that the electro-optical converter was being disturbed by noise on the twisted pair conducting or radiating inside the converter.

Section 5 describes the experiment and the interpretation of the data. The interpretation assumed that the EMI disturbance appeared with some fixed probability for each control cycle and that the disturbance lasted exactly one control cycle. A relationship

with the field data is made by computing the maximum disturbance probability that preserves asymptotic stability.

This experiment was conducted in a HIRF (High Intensity Radiated Field) Chamber that was recently constructed at NASA Langley Research Center. Obviously, more development is needed (and planned) for both chamber operation and equipment under test. Nevertheless, the HIRF Chamber did provide a realistic electromagnetic environment. The chamber did disturb a simple communication system, and it was possible to determine the nature of the disturbance. Most important, it provided a proof-of-concept experiment for a recent result about stability in the presence of controller perturbations. The experiment showed that it is possible to observe the parameters required by the theory and make conclusions about plant stability.

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Allan L. White received a Ph. D. in mathematics from New Mexico State University. He has taught at the University of Colorado. He was an applied mathematician at Kentron International, Inc. He is now at NASA Langley Research Center. His interests include the design and analysis of process control systems.

Hagbae Kim received the B.S. degree from in Electronics Engineering from Seoul National University, Seoul, Korea, in 1988, and the M.S. and ph.D. degrees in Electrical Engineering and Computer Science from the University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, in 1990 and 1994, respectively.

Currently, he is a National Research Council (NRC) resident research associate at NASA Langley Research Center, Hampton, Virginia. His research interest includes real-time control systems, manufacturing systems, fault-tolerant computing, reliability modeling, and probability and stochastic processes.